

Digital Resource Acquisition as A Determinant of Collection Development in Academic Libraries in Ogun State

By

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Abstract

This study examined digital resource acquisition and collection development practices in academic libraries in Ogun State, Nigeria; specifically, to determine the level of digital resource acquisition and collection development practices in academic libraries. Descriptive survey research design was adopted, and total enumeration was used to include all 107 librarians from seven selected academic libraries. Data were collected using a self-structured, closed-ended questionnaire created on Google Forms, ensuring ease of access and completion by respondents. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation) and Pearson Product Moment Correlation with the aid of SPSS version 26. Findings revealed a moderate level of digital resource acquisition among librarians ($\bar{x} = 2.85$), with particular strengths in resource evaluation, selection, and staff training. The study also found that collection development practices are moderate ($\bar{x} = 2.85$), with strengths in considering user needs, documenting policies, and enhancing accessibility. Additionally, there is a weak positive relationship between digital resource acquisition and collection development ($r = .462^$, $p < 0.05$), which implies that higher engagement in digital resource acquisition is likely associated with stronger and more relevant collections. The study concludes that while academic libraries in Ogun State are progressively integrating digital resources, sustained efforts are needed to achieve more effective collection development and service delivery. Based on these findings, it was recommended that libraries invest in regular staff training, ensure consistent funding, develop comprehensive collection development policies, integrate acquisition processes with collection assessment tools, and foster collaboration with other libraries.*

Keywords: Digital resource acquisition, Collection development, academic libraries

Introduction

Academic libraries play a vital role in

supporting teaching, learning, and research in higher education institutions. They serve as

information hubs where students, lecturers, and researchers access scholarly materials required for academic success. Traditionally, academic libraries focused mainly on the acquisition and management of print resources such as textbooks, journals, newspapers, theses, and reference materials. These materials were acquired through direct purchase, gifts, exchanges, and legal deposit, and were physically housed within library buildings for users to consult (Oliveira & Cunha, 2024). Collection development during this period was guided by institutional goals, user needs, subject relevance, and available funds, with librarians carefully selecting materials to build balanced and relevant collections. Before the emergence of digital technologies, traditional acquisition processes involved manual selection tools such as publishers' catalogues, book reviews, faculty recommendations, and approval plans. Librarians evaluated materials based on factors such as relevance to curriculum, durability, cost, and space availability (Rathod, 2025).

Collection development policies focused largely on print materials and emphasized ownership rather than access. Although this system served academic communities for many years, it had limitations, including slow access to

information, physical space constraints, limited copies of materials, and difficulties in sharing resources across institutions (Xin & Xingdong, 2023). The rapid growth of information and advances in information and communication technology (ICT) have significantly transformed academic libraries. The shift from print-based collections to digital resources has changed how libraries acquire, manage, and provide access to information. Digital resources such as e-books, e-journals, online databases, institutional repositories, and multimedia resources now form a core part of academic library collections (Sodipe et al., 2025). These resources allow users to access information remotely, support online and blended learning, and provide up-to-date scholarly content without geographical limitations (Umar, 2025).

Digital resource acquisition refers to the process through which academic libraries identify, select, license, and provide access to electronic information resources. Unlike traditional acquisition, digital acquisition focuses more on licensing and access rather than ownership. Librarians must consider factors such as subscription costs, license agreements, access rights, copyright compliance, platform usability, and long-term sustainability when acquiring digital

resources (Samaila, 2025). According to Winifred et al. (2022), effective digital acquisition ensures that libraries provide timely, reliable, and relevant resources that meet users' academic and research needs. Collection development in the digital era goes beyond simply acquiring materials. It involves systematic planning, continuous evaluation, and effective management of both print and electronic resources to support institutional goals (Rajkumar & Sitwala, 2025). Digital collection development requires libraries to adopt hybrid strategies that integrate traditional print resources with electronic materials. This integration helps libraries remain relevant while responding to changing user preferences and learning environments. Well-developed digital collections improve research productivity, enhance learning outcomes, and increase user satisfaction (Sodipe et al., 2024).

To guide digital resource acquisition and collection development, academic libraries rely on comprehensive collection development policies. These policies outline the principles, criteria, and procedures for selecting, acquiring, evaluating, and managing library resources. In the digital context, collection development policies address issues such as licensing terms, access models, cost control, preservation, and user

access rights (Oliveira & Cunha, 2024). According to Sodipe et al. (2025), libraries with clear and up-to-date policies are better positioned to manage digital resources effectively and ensure consistency in decision-making. Such policies also help libraries align their collections with institutional priorities and available budgets. Another important aspect of digital resource acquisition and collection development is the use of collection assessment tools. These tools help libraries evaluate the relevance, usage, and impact of their collections. Common collection assessment tools include usage statistics from databases, circulation records, user surveys, citation analysis, and feedback from faculty and students (Abhishek & Sharma, 2025). Integrating acquisition processes with these assessment tools enables librarians to make informed decisions about renewing subscriptions, cancelling underused resources, and acquiring new materials that better meet user needs (Xin & Xingdong, 2023).

Collaboration has also become a key strategy in digital resource acquisition and collection development. Academic libraries increasingly establish collaborative networks with other libraries to share digital resources, reduce costs, and improve access. Through consortia and inter-institutional agreements,

libraries can jointly subscribe to databases, share institutional repositories, and exchange best practices in digital collection management (Ashilungu & Onyancha, 2024). Examples include library consortia where member institutions pool resources to negotiate better licensing terms with publishers. Such collaboration enhances resource availability while minimizing financial burdens, especially in developing regions (Belsare & Achalpur, 2025). In Nigeria, academic libraries face unique challenges in digital resource acquisition and collection development. Issues such as inadequate funding, unstable internet connectivity, limited ICT infrastructure, and insufficient staff training often hinder effective digital library services (Gandung et al., 2025). Despite efforts to adopt library management systems and electronic databases, many libraries still struggle to provide adequate access to digital resources for their users. These challenges underscore the need for effective acquisition strategies, strong collection development policies, and collaborative approaches tailored to the local context. Ogun State is home to several federal, state, and private universities, making it an important hub for higher education in Nigeria. Academic libraries in the state serve diverse user populations with

varying academic and research needs. The selection of academic libraries for this study was based on their institutional type (federal, state, and private universities) and their active engagement in digital library services. This approach ensures a balanced representation of academic libraries in Ogun State and provides a broader understanding of digital resource acquisition and collection development practices across different institutional settings. The increasing demand for online learning, remote research, and access to current academic materials has placed additional pressure on academic libraries in Ogun State. Students and researchers now expect seamless access to digital resources at any time and from any location. However, limitations in funding, infrastructure, and policy implementation may affect libraries' ability to meet these expectations (Sodipe et al., 2024).

Digital resources contribute significantly to teaching, learning, and research by providing flexible access to information and supporting innovative learning methods such as e-learning, blended learning, and virtual research collaboration (Umar, 2025). Belsare and Achalpur (2025) observed that effective digital collections enhance academic productivity by enabling faster information retrieval and broader

access to scholarly materials. Continuous evaluation and adaptation of digital collections ensure that libraries remain responsive to evolving user needs and technological advancements (Rajkumar & Sitwala, 2025). In view of these developments, examining digital resource acquisition and collection development in academic libraries in Ogun State is both timely and necessary.

Statement of the Problem

Digital resource acquisition and collection development in academic libraries may be facing significant challenges due to the rapid growth of information and the shift from traditional print to electronic resources. Many academic libraries probably struggle with inadequate funding, limited ICT infrastructure, and insufficient staff training, which likely affects the availability and accessibility of digital resources for students and researchers. Moreover, the increasing demand for online learning, remote research, and access to up-to-date academic materials may have placed additional pressure on library management, exposing gaps in acquisition strategies and collection development policies. In addition, previous efforts such as adoption of library management software, training of staff, and collaboration with faculty members have

probably not fully resolved these issues, leaving some students and researchers with limited access to essential digital resources. Similarly, studies indicate that many collection development policies inadequately address licensing, access provision, and cost considerations for digital resources, which may hinder effective library services. Hence, it is therefore imperative to investigate digital resource acquisition and collection development in academic libraries in Ogun state. Specifically, the study intend to determine the level of digital resource acquisition in academic libraries; assess the level of collection development practices in academic libraries; examine the content of the collection development policies, and examine the relationship between digital resource acquisition and collection development in academic libraries in Ogun state.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in order to guide the study.

- (i) What is the level of digital resource acquisition in academic libraries in Ogun state?
- (ii) What is the level of collection development practices in academic libraries in Ogun state?

- (iii) What are the content of the collection development policies in academic libraries in Ogun state?
- (iv) What is the relationship between digital resource acquisition and collection development in academic libraries in Ogun state?

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The design was considered appropriate because it allows the researcher to collect data from a defined population in order to describe existing conditions, opinions, and practices related to digital resource acquisition and collection

development in academic libraries. The survey approach made it possible to obtain first-hand information from librarians across different universities in Ogun State.

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised all librarians working in the selected academic libraries in Ogun State, Nigeria. A total of seven (7) academic libraries were involved in the study, cutting across federal, state, and private universities. The total population of librarians in these libraries was one hundred and seven (107), as obtained from the librarians’ offices of the respective institutions.

Table 1: Population Distribution of the study

S/N	Name of Institutions	Name of the Library	Number of Librarians
1	Babcock University	Laz Otti Memorial library	18
2	Bells University of Technology	Adenuga library	9
3	Olabisi Onabanjo University	Olabisi Onabanjo University library	11
4	Tai Solarin Federal University of Education	Gbenga Daniel library	13
5	Christopher University	Nelson Mandela library	11
6	Covenant University	Centre for learning resources	22
7	Federal University of Agriculture	Nimbe Adedipe library	23
Total			107

Source: Librarians’ office in each of the selected libraries

Sample and Sampling Technique

Due to the relatively small size of the population, the study adopted a total

enumeration sampling technique, where all the librarians in the selected academic libraries were included in the study. This

method ensured that every librarian had an equal opportunity to participate and helped improve the reliability and representativeness of the findings.

Research Instrument

A self-structured, closed-ended questionnaire was used to collect data. The questionnaire was created using **Google Forms** to make it easy for respondents to access and complete online.

Procedure for Data Collection

The questionnaire link was shared with librarians through email and social media platforms such as WhatsApp groups

and mails. Respondents were encouraged to complete the form honestly and submit it promptly. Follow-up reminders were sent weekly for two weeks to increase the response rate. This online method ensured faster, wider, and more efficient data collection without physical visits to the libraries.

Method of Data Analysis

The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS version 26) was used to arrange and illustrate the data using a descriptive statistic (frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation) and Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC).

Results Presentation

Research Question 1: What is the level of digital resource acquisition in academic libraries in Ogun state?

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis of RQ One

S/N	Items	SA (4)	A (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	Mean (\bar{X})	Std. Dev. (SD)
1	The library regularly evaluates digital resources before acquisition.	36 (33.6%)	34 (31.8%)	20 (18.7%)	17 (15.9%)	2.92	1.04
2	Digital resources are selected based on the academic needs of students and staff.	38 (35.5%)	32 (29.9%)	21 (19.6%)	16 (15.0%)	2.94	1.03
3	Licensing agreements for digital resources are properly negotiated before purchase.	34 (31.8%)	33 (30.8%)	22 (20.6%)	18 (16.8%)	2.84	1.07

4	The library subscribes to relevant electronic journals and databases consistently.	37 (34.6%)	31 (29.0%)	23 (21.5%)	16 (15.0%)	2.86	1.03
5	Procurement of digital resources is timely to meet academic demands.	35 (32.7%)	34 (31.8%)	21 (19.6%)	17 (15.9%)	2.85	1.06
6	The library monitors the usage of acquired digital resources to inform future purchases.	33 (30.8%)	36 (33.6%)	20 (18.7%)	18 (16.8%)	2.81	1.07
7	Vendors are consulted to ensure quality and reliability of digital resources.	32 (29.9%)	35 (32.7%)	22 (20.6%)	18 (16.8%)	2.79	1.08
8	Budget allocation for digital resources is sufficient for current needs.	31 (28.9%)	34 (31.8%)	23 (21.5%)	19 (17.8%)	2.74	1.10
9	Staff members are trained to handle the acquisition process effectively.	36 (33.6%)	33 (30.8%)	21 (19.6%)	17 (15.9%)	2.88	1.05
10	Feedback from students and faculty influences decisions on acquiring digital resources.	35 (32.7%)	32 (29.9%)	23 (21.5%)	17 (15.9%)	2.84	1.06
Average Mean						2.85	1.06

Decision Rule: 1.00–1.45 = Strongly Disagree (SD); 1.46–2.30 = Disagree (D); 2.31–3.15 = Agree (A); 3.16–4.00 = Strongly Agree (SA)

The results in Table 1 show that among the items, the highest mean was for digital resources being selected based on academic needs (Mean = 2.94). Similarly, staff training for acquisition (Mean = 2.88) and evaluation of digital resources (Mean = 2.92) were

notable. Lower means were observed for budget sufficiency (Mean = 2.74) and vendor consultation (Mean = 2.79). With an average mean score of 2.85, which is above the decision threshold of 2.50, it can be adjudged that the level of digital resource acquisition in

academic libraries is moderate. Hence, there is moderate level of digital resource acquisition among librarians in academic

libraries in Ogun state, with strengths in resource evaluation, selection, and staff training.

Research Question 2: What is the level of collection development practices in academic libraries in Ogun state?

Table 2: Descriptive Analysis of RQ Two

S/N	Items	SA (4)	A (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	Mean (\bar{X})	Std. Dev. (SD)
1	Collection development policies are clearly documented and regularly updated.	36 (33.6%)	35 (32.7%)	20 (18.7%)	16 (15.0%)	2.87	1.05
2	User needs are considered when developing the library's collection.	38 (35.5%)	34 (31.8%)	18 (16.8%)	17 (15.9%)	2.91	1.05
3	Institutional priorities guide the selection of library resources.	35 (32.7%)	33 (30.8%)	21 (19.6%)	18 (16.8%)	2.84	1.07
4	There is a proper balance between print and digital resources in the library.	33 (30.8%)	36 (33.6%)	20 (18.7%)	18 (16.8%)	2.81	1.07
5	The library ensures that resources are current, relevant, and reliable.	37 (34.6%)	33 (30.8%)	21 (19.6%)	16 (15.0%)	2.88	1.04
6	Preservation strategies are applied to maintain long-term accessibility of resources.	32 (29.9%)	34 (31.8%)	22 (20.6%)	19 (17.8%)	2.75	1.09
7	Collaboration with faculty helps improve the quality of collection development.	36 (33.6%)	32 (29.9%)	21 (19.6%)	18 (16.8%)	2.85	1.07

8	Periodic reviews are conducted to identify gaps in the library's collection.	35 (32.7%)	33 (30.8%)	23 (21.5%)	16 (15.0%)	2.83	1.06
9	Policies are in place to acquire resources in emerging or specialized areas.	34 (31.8%)	33 (30.8%)	22 (20.6%)	18 (16.8%)	2.81	1.07
10	The library promotes accessibility of resources to all users effectively.	37 (34.6%)	32 (29.9%)	20 (18.7%)	18 (16.8%)	2.87	1.06
Average Mean						2.85	1.06

Decision Rule: 1.00–1.45 = Strongly Disagree (SD); 1.46–2.30 = Disagree (D); 2.31–3.15 = Agree (A); 3.16–4.00 = Strongly Agree (SA)

The results in Table 2 indicate that among the items, the highest mean was for user needs being considered in collection development (Mean = 2.91). Similarly, collection policies being documented and regularly updated (Mean = 2.87) and promotion of accessibility to all users (Mean = 2.87) were significant. With an average mean score of 2.85, which is above the decision threshold of 2.50, it can be

adjudged that the level of collection development practices in academic libraries in Ogun State is moderate. Hence, there is moderate level of collection development practices among librarians in academic libraries in Ogun state, with strengths in user consideration, policy documentation, and accessibility.

Research Question 3: What is the content of the collection development policies in academic libraries in Ogun state?

Table 3: Descriptive Analysis of RQ Three

S/N	Items	SA (4)	A (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	Mean (\bar{X})	Std. Dev. (SD)
1	The library has a written collection development policy that guides the selection of digital resources.	43 (40.2%)	35 (32.7%)	17 (15.9%)	12 (11.2%)	3.02	1.00
2	The collection development policy clearly states the goals and objectives for acquiring digital resources.	41 (38.3%)	37 (34.6%)	18 (16.8%)	11 (10.3%)	3.03	0.98
3	The policy outlines the criteria used for selecting electronic books, journals, and databases.	45 (42.1%)	33 (30.8%)	18 (16.8%)	11 (10.3%)	3.05	1.01
4	The collection development policy includes guidelines for evaluating the quality and relevance of digital resources before acquisition.	39 (36.4%)	38 (35.5%)	19 (17.8%)	11 (10.3%)	3.00	0.97
5	The policy explains the roles and responsibilities of librarians in selecting and acquiring digital resources.	37 (34.6%)	40 (37.4%)	19 (17.8%)	11 (10.3%)	2.97	0.95
6	The collection development policy contains provisions for budgeting and funding digital resource acquisition.	40 (37.4%)	36 (33.6%)	20 (18.7%)	11 (10.3%)	2.98	0.99
7	The policy includes procedures for reviewing and updating digital resources regularly.	38 (35.5%)	39 (36.4%)	19 (17.8%)	11 (10.3%)	2.97	0.96
8	The collection development policy provides guidelines for handling subscription	36 (33.6%)	41 (38.3%)	19 (17.8%)	11 (10.3%)	2.96	0.94

renewals and cancellations of digital resources.

9	The policy addresses user needs and feedback when making decisions about digital resource acquisition.	42 (39.3%)	34 (31.8%)	20 (18.7%)	11 (10.3%)	3.00	1.00
10	The collection development policy includes standards for ensuring access, licensing, and copyright compliance for digital resources.	44 (41.1%)	33 (30.8%)	19 (17.8%)	11 (10.3%)	3.03	1.01
Average Mean						3.00	0.98

Decision Rule: 1.00–1.45 = Strongly Disagree (SD); 1.46–2.30 = Disagree (D); 2.31–3.15 = Agree (A); 3.16–4.00 = Strongly Agree (SA)

The results in Table 3 reveal that all the items had mean scores above the decision benchmark of 2.50, indicating that respondents agreed that collection development policies in academic libraries in Ogun State contain relevant components related to digital resource acquisition. The highest mean score was recorded for the policy outlining criteria for selecting electronic books, journals, and databases (Mean = 3.05). This was followed closely by the clarity of policy goals and objectives (Mean = 3.03) and standards for ensuring access, licensing, and copyright compliance

(Mean = 3.03). The average mean score of 3.00, which is above the decision threshold of 2.50, indicates that the content of collection development policies in the libraries studied is adequate. Hence, academic libraries in Ogun State have comprehensive collection development policies that sufficiently address key areas of digital resource acquisition such as selecting electronic books, journals and databases; clearly stating the goals and objectives for acquiring digital resources, as well as ensuring access, licensing, and copyright compliance for digital resources.

Research Question 4: What is the relationship between digital resource acquisition and collection development in academic libraries in Ogun State?

Table 4: Pearson’s Correlation of digital resource acquisition and collection development

Variables	N	Mean	S.D	df	r	Sig.
Digital resource acquisition	107	32.74	4.12	105	.462*	.000
Collection development	107	33.21	3.87			

Table 3 shows a weak positive relationship ($r = .462$, $df = 105$, $p < .05$) between digital resource acquisition and collection development in academic libraries in Ogun State. This implies that higher levels of digital resource acquisition are likely

Discussion of the Findings

The study showed that there is moderate level of digital resource acquisition among librarians in academic libraries in Ogun state, with strengths in resource evaluation, selection, and staff training. This finding aligns with the study of Sodipe, Arinola, Aliyu, and Bamgbose (2025), who asserted that academic libraries in South-West Nigeria actively employ policies and trained personnel to manage electronic resources, though challenges with infrastructure and access remain. Similarly, Deshpande and Waray (2024) emphasized that effective acquisition involves systematic evaluation and selection of e-resources, highlighting the importance of staff competence in navigating digital formats,

associated with better collection development practices. In practice, the level of digital acquisition in the libraries is influence less by collection development policies while majority of the influence are as a result of other factors.

which supports the observed strength in staff training in this study. In contrast, Umar (2025) reported that adoption of digital libraries in Nigeria is often limited by low digital literacy and weak institutional frameworks, suggesting that the moderate level observed in Ogun State may reflect partial mitigation of these barriers rather than full effectiveness. Belsare and Achalpur (2025) also highlighted that digital libraries transform traditional library services and demand continuous staff development, reinforcing the need for ongoing training observed in this study. Sodipe, Ukangwa, Adebisi and Olutoki (2025) further argued that collaboration among libraries and adoption of 4IR technologies can improve resource acquisition, indicating that moderate

acquisition levels may be enhanced through interlibrary partnerships. Conversely, Samaila (2025) noted that inadequate funding and limited ICT infrastructure often hinder optimal acquisition, which may explain why the level observed is moderate rather than high.

The study revealed that there is moderate level of collection development practices among librarians in academic libraries in Ogun state, with strengths in user consideration, policy documentation, and accessibility. This finding aligns with Rajkumar and Sitwala (2025), who asserted that academic libraries aim to align collection development practices with student learning needs and institutional priorities, though challenges with funding and policy implementation remain. Winifred (2025) reported that collection development policies often inadequately address electronic resources, suggesting that the moderate level observed may result from partial adherence to policy frameworks rather than comprehensive implementation. Similarly, Ashilungu and Onyancha (2024) emphasized the importance of faculty-librarian collaboration in enhancing collection development, which reinforces the observed strength in considering user input in Ogun State libraries. In contrast, Kamau and

Elegwa (2021) argued that institutional and technological factors frequently constrain collection development, indicating that the moderate practices observed may reflect structural limitations in academic libraries. Oliveira and Cunha (2024) highlighted that digital collections require careful planning regarding licensing, access, and technical feasibility, which suggests that Ogun State librarians may be performing adequately but not optimally in managing complex digital resources. Finally, Tausif and Mushtaq (2020) noted that inadequate training and infrastructural challenges hinder electronic resource management, indicating that moderate collection development levels may be a product of resource and capacity limitations.

The study revealed that academic libraries in Ogun State have comprehensive collection development policies that sufficiently address key areas of digital resource acquisition such as selecting electronic books, journals and databases; clearly stating the goals and objectives for acquiring digital resources, as well as ensuring access, licensing, and copyright compliance for digital resources. This finding aligns with the study of Oliveira and Cunha (2024) who asserted that well-structured collection development policies provide clear

guidance for resource selection, acquisition procedures, and access management in academic libraries. Similarly, Sodipe et al. (2025) emphasized that libraries with clearly documented policies are more effective in managing digital collections and ensuring consistency in decision-making, which supports the present finding. In the same vein, Samaila (2025) maintained that digital resource acquisition requires careful attention to licensing agreements, access rights, and sustainability considerations, which are typically addressed through comprehensive policies. Furthermore, Rajkumar and Sitwala (2025) argued that systematic planning through policy frameworks strengthens digital collection development and aligns resources with institutional goals, reinforcing the current result. However, this finding is not entirely in line with Gandung et al. (2025) who reported that many academic libraries in developing regions struggle with weak policy implementation due to funding and infrastructure challenges, suggesting that the effectiveness of policies may vary across contexts.

The study showed that there is a weak positive relationship between digital resource acquisition and collection development in academic libraries in Ogun State, which implies that higher levels of digital resource

acquisition are likely associated with better collection development practices. This finding is in line with Sodipe, Amalahu, Uthman, and Safiriyu (2024), who asserted that libraries leveraging digital tools for resource acquisition often enhance the overall management and relevance of their collections. Similarly, Belsare and Achalpur (2025) argued that digital libraries facilitate improved resource accessibility and integration, supporting the idea that acquisition practices positively influence collection development. Rajkumar and Sitwala (2025) highlighted that strategic electronic resource acquisition enables libraries to meet user needs and institutional priorities, reinforcing the observed correlation. In contrast, Winifred (2025) pointed out that poorly structured collection development policies may limit the benefits of digital acquisition, suggesting that the positive relationship may not automatically guarantee optimal collection outcomes. Sodipe, Ukangwa, Adebisi and Olutoki (2025) emphasized the role of collaboration and 4IR technologies in aligning acquisitions with collection goals, indicating that the observed moderate relationship could be strengthened through cooperative strategies. Finally, Deshpande and Waray (2024) noted that challenges in acquisition, including

limited staff skills and insufficient infrastructure, can dampen the effectiveness of collection development, which explains why the relationship is moderate rather than strong.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, academic librarians in Ogun State exhibit a moderate level of digital resource acquisition, indicating that while librarians are actively engaging in evaluating, selecting, and procuring digital resources, there are still limitations likely due to infrastructure, funding, and digital skills gaps. Libraries are making deliberate efforts to integrate digital tools into their services, but the full potential of digital resource acquisition has not yet been realized. Academic libraries have comprehensive collection development policies that sufficiently address key areas of digital resource acquisition such as selecting electronic books, journals and databases; clearly stating the goals and objectives for acquiring digital resources, as well as ensuring access, licensing, and copyright compliance for digital resources. Librarians consider user needs, document policies, and enhance accessibility, yet challenges such as inconsistent policy implementation and limited resources may prevent optimal

performance. This indicates that academic libraries are prioritizing user-centered practices but still face barriers that hinder fully effective collection management. Libraries that invest more in acquiring digital resources tend to maintain stronger and more relevant collections.

Based on the findings, it is therefore recommended that academic libraries in Ogun State invest more in staff capacity building through regular training workshops on emerging digital resources and technologies, and also ensure consistent funding to enable the procurement of diverse and up-to-date digital materials. Regarding collection development practices, libraries should develop comprehensive and regularly reviewed collection development policies that incorporate both print and digital resources, and actively involve faculty and users in the selection and evaluation of resources to enhance relevance and accessibility. Concerning the relationship between digital resource acquisition and collection development, it is recommended that libraries adopt integrated management systems linking acquisition processes with collection assessment tools, and establish collaborative networks with other libraries to share digital resources and best practices for effective collection development.

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